

1 **Immune co-receptors for liver-endogenous TRA.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We performed transcriptomic discovery here for immune co-receptors for liver-endogenous TRA
7 (tissue-restricted antigen) that signal presence of self.

8 **Results**

9 1. Immune receptors co-regulated with TRA specific for the liver organ system that signal
10 immunologic presence of self.

- 11 a. Lrrm4
- 12 b. Flrt3
- 13 c. Clec1b
- 14 d. Lypd1
- 15 e. Kel
- 16 f. Prr15l
- 17 g. Igsf1
- 18 h. Gypb
- 19 i. Lrrc6c
- 20 j. Ly6g6d

21 2. A set of cell surface markers that distinguish the FGA/FGB/FGG-expressed milieu.

- 22 a. Gpr
 - 23 i. Gpr37
 - 24 ii. Gpr126
 - 25 iii. Gpr128
 - 26 iv. Gpr143
 - 27 v. Gpr87
 - 28 vi. Gpr39
 - vii. Gpr98
 - viii. Gpr56
 - ix. Gpr183
 - x. Gpr26
 - xi. Gpr88
- b. Tmem
 - i. Tmem88
 - ii. Tmem2
 - iii. Tmem37
 - iv. Tmem176b
 - v. Tmem51
 - vi. Tmem176a
 - vii. Tmem27

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- viii. Tmem45b
- ix. Tmem144
- x. Tmem100

- c. Fam
 - i. Fam89a
 - ii. Fam176a
 - iii. Fam159a
 - iv. Fam211a
 - v. Fam108b1
 - vi. Fam26e
 - vii. Fam174
 - viii. Fam211b
 - ix. Fam98b
 - x. Fam43a

Citations

1. Stel, H.V., Van der Kwast, T.H. and Veerman, E.C.I., 1983. Detection of factor VIII/coagulant antigen in human liver tissue. *Nature*, 303(5917), pp.530-532.